

Early Detection of Defects in Machine Learning Programs by Semi-Static Analysis

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Abstract—Machine learning (ML) has transformed various fields, highlighting the importance of early defect detection in ML programs without executing the code. While static analysis presents opportunities, existing studies have limitations. Meanwhile, notebooks have become a popular platform for developing ML prototypes. Notably, notebooks offer valuable run-time information, which can potentially enhance static analysis. In this project, we propose a semi-static analysis approach that will leverage available notebook run-time information. Our techniques will incorporate abstract interpretation with ML-based methods and support both notebooks and scripts. Our goal is to deliver efficient and effective semi-static analysis methodologies and open-source tools for the early detection of defects during coding, to enhance the productivity of ML development and the quality of ML programs.

I. MOTIVATION

Background. Machine learning (ML) techniques, including deep learning (DL) methods, have revolutionized various fields. However, developing ML programs can be challenging, especially for practitioners without a software development background. The complexity of ML systems is compounded by dynamic-typing languages (e.g. Python), ML model constructions, and software code [1]. The common use of ML libraries adds another layer of complexity and increases the risk of defects due to misinterpretation or misuse.

Significance. ML models, particularly DL models, often require significant computational resources for training. Defects in the code can lead to program failures after prolonged execution, resulting in reduced productivity and wasted resources [2]. Undetected bugs can also lead to misleading results and threaten safety-critical systems. Therefore, it is essential to develop efficient and effective static analysis techniques for ML defect detection during coding, before execution.

Run-time information. Notebooks (e.g. Jupyter Notebooks) have emerged as a popular platform for data analysis and prototyping ML models before deployment in production [3]. Supporting the development process and promoting the correctness of ML prototypes can mitigate technical debt in the delivery of large ML projects. Furthermore, notebooks offer flexibility in executing code in cells, which yields more complex situations for revealing defects but also provides valuable run-time information that can enhance static analysis.

Hypothesis: Run-time information of ML programs can be exploited to make static analyzers faster and more effective.

II. STATE-OF-THE-ART

Static analysis. Static analysis examines code for defects without execution. Abstract interpretation-based methods have been widely used for traditional software [4]. Recently, ML models have been adapted to static analysis. Abstract interpretation aims for soundness but may have false alarms, while ML methods generate fewer false alarms but may overlook certain errors. ML-based static analysis also lacks explainability and faces challenges in limited benchmark datasets [5].

Static analysis for ML code. Current static analysis studies for ML programs primarily focus on tensor shape mismatches in TensorFlow [6], [7] and PyTorch [8], or API misuses [9]. However, a substantial number of ML code defects remain unaddressed [10]. Moreover, code annotations are often required for solving types and shapes [6], [7]. ML-based techniques, although hosted in general Python programs (e.g. type inference [11], name-value inconsistencies [12]) have not been extensively explored in ML defect detection.

Static analysis in notebooks. For ML notebooks, Liblit et al. [13] detect notebook-specific issues and API misuses in PyTorch but do not provide real-time assistance. On the other hand, Subotic et al. [14] develop an abstract interpretation-based framework for notebook integration but it is not tailored to ML programs and lacks open-source tools. Moreover, they do not use available run-time information, resulting in over-approximated results and longer overhead.

Key limitations. Existing approaches focus on limited ML defect types in specific, often outdated libraries. Code annotations are often required for unknown types or shapes, increasing human efforts.

III. OBJECTIVES

Objective: To enhance the quality of ML programs, this project aims to propose a *semi-static* analysis approach for the early and effective detection of defects in ML code by exploiting run-time information.

The following research questions will be investigated:

- RQ1** What types of defects in ML programs can be effectively detected through static analysis techniques?
- RQ2** How to exploit run-time information in notebooks to enhance static analysis for ML programs?
- RQ3** What is the trade-off between the effectiveness and scalability of static analyzers for ML programs?

IV. SCIENTIFIC APPROACH

Our semi-static approach includes abstract interpretation and ML-based static analysis methods. ML notebooks will be initially experimented with by using run-time information, followed by an investigation of entire ML programs. The research agenda contains the following objectives:

- O1** Identify and prioritize ML defects based on previous studies and recent public ML projects.
- O2** Reveal defects in ML programs in notebooks by exploiting run-time information during static analysis.
- O3** Detect defects in ML scripts by combining abstract interpretation and ML-based static analysis methods.
- O4** Design configurable, parametric static analyzers to control the trade-off between effectiveness and scalability.
- O5** Develop open-source static analyzers for ML programs.
- O6** Conduct extensive evaluation of scalability and effectiveness of static analyzers for ML programs.

These objectives are aligned with the research questions.

RQ1. The initial taxonomy of ML defects [15] will be analyzed and complemented with recent ML projects (**O1**). Defects will be prioritized based on frequency, severity, and detectability. The detection process involves extracting intermediate representations from the code or ML notebooks, constructing dependency graphs, and rule designing (**O2**, **O3**). Detection algorithms (e.g. constraint solving, graph pattern matching) will be developed and generate alerts with priorities.

RQ2. Constraint solvers will be initially used for ML notebooks (**O2**). For unknown shapes and unsolvable types, rule-based methods with notebook run-time information will provide further clarification. Meanwhile, data (e.g. code statements and context, clarified shape or type, analysis results) will be collected to fine-tune a sequence-to-sequence ML model [11]. It will be used for ML programs with no run-time information (**O3**). An abstract interpretation-based static analyzer will also be employed to compensate for the explainability.

RQ3. To assist users during coding in notebooks and script editors without disrupting the development flow, the static analyzers will be implemented as parametric tools to investigate the trade-off between effectiveness and the introduced overhead (**O4**). Configurable settings, such as contextual information (e.g. call sites, number of execution paths), and the depth of cell dependence in notebooks, will be considered.

Evaluation. The static analyzers will be comprehensively evaluated on open-source datasets and publicly available ML code (e.g. language models, generative networks) (**O6**). The evaluation will focus on *scalability* by measuring analysis time, and *effectiveness* by assessing accuracy and precision. The datasets will be published to promote reproducibility.

Tooling and open science. To increase practical relevance, scalable open-source tools will also be developed (**O5**). The static analyzers will be designed as an extension for notebook applications and as code editor plugins with real-time feedback to engineers. Additionally, the project will provide and maintain open datasets and benchmarks for further research.

V. PROGRESS AND PLAN

After starting in February 2023, I have extensively studied existing research and performed initial feasibility tests to identify limitations and research gaps. This forms a strong foundation for the proposed research. Moving forward, the proposed methods will be conducted to contribute to the development of a novel semi-static analysis approach and open-source tools for the early defect detection of ML programs.

Acknowledgement. This research is supervised by Profs. Dániel Varró and Ulf Nilsson, and partially supported by the Wallenberg AI, Autonomous Systems and Software Program (WASP) funded by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation.

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Presented at the 38th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering (ASE 2023) - Doctoral Forum